

Review

Epidemiology of the HPV in Greece and other Countries of the World

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Abstract

Cervical cancer is the fourth most common type of cancer among women worldwide. It is estimated that more than half a million women are infected by an HPV genotype. The purpose of the epidemiological review is to determine the prevalence of human papillomavirus (HPV) infection and the distribution of its genotypes among various countries worldwide, as well as in Greece and to record the characteristics of the subtype incidence. We recorded published studies concerning epidemiological data of the prevalence of the HPV subtypes, according to the geographical location and HPV detection rates for both healthy and infected women. The studies were heterogeneous with regard to sample selection. The prevalence of any subtype of the HPV is about 11%. HPV16 is the most common genotype reported in most countries. The substantial differences in the prevalence and distribution of the virus among the various geographical sites, deserve further analysis in global epidemiological studies, including populations with common characteristics.

Keywords: Developing countries, Developed countries, Greece, HPV, Prevalence

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INTRODUCTION

HPV (Human Papilloma Virus) is one of the most common viruses worldwide today. It is responsible for sexual transmitted diseases, affecting millions of men and women throughout the world, as well as for the development of cervical cancer. The relationship between HPV and cervical cancer, as a result of a long-lasting irreversible infection by specific strains of the virus (Bosch et al., 2002), is indisputable over the past thirty-five years. Cervical cancer is the third most common type of cancer among women worldwide in developed countries. It is estimated that approximately 530000 new cases are diagnosed each year and 275000 deaths are recorded, most of them occurring in developed countries (Forman et al., 2012; Bosch et al., 2013).

Most HPV infections are transmitted after close skin or transmucosal contact. Sexual contact primarily and autoinoculation in addition with the aid of hands that come into contact with mucous membranes and perinatal

or intrauterine dissemination of the virus from the mother to the fetus, are the main transmission pathways of the HPV infection. Sexual intercourse is the major route of the HPV transmission to the rectum. HPV infection is more common among sexually active adolescents and younger women, remaining rare though in sexually inactive women (Scheurer et al., 2005; Moscicki, 2007). The increased incidence of HPV infection in young women is very likely to be related to the frequent rotation of sexual partners that characterize these age groups. Recent studies have indicated that sexual behavior increases significantly the risk of HPV infection (Dunne et al., 2007).

The persistent infection with high risk HPV subtypes, the development of high-grade cervical intraepithelial lesions and in situ carcinoma, as well as invasive cancer subsequently, are now considered to be the necessary prerequisites in cervical carcinogenesis. It is estimated

that the more the HPV infection persists, the higher the chance of carcinogenicity. The most prominent risk factor for the progression of HPV infection to neoplasia and cervical cancer, is the persistent HPV infection by a high-risk strain of the virus (Yokoyama et al., 2003). Prospective studies have demonstrated that the persistence of HPV infection reduces the likelihood of self-purification and increases the risk of developing pre-cancerous lesions (Plummer et al., 2007).

HPV Infection Prevalence

The prevalence of HPV infection has been extensively investigated in recent years. The knowledge of the HPV prevalence is estimated to contribute significantly to the modernization of the primary cervical cancer prevention programs, as well as to the provision of better quality health services at the lowest cost (Dempsey et al., 2006; Fu et al., 2014). The widely accepted notion nowadays that cervical cancer results almost exclusively from HPV infection, has led the scientific community to take measures, in order to prevent the spread of the virus. Worldwide, cervical cancer is considered to be the third most common type of cancer among women and the seventh of all forms, with more than 500000 to 530000 new cases per year (Arbyn et al., 2010).

The prevalence of the HPV in women with normal cytological findings worldwide is estimated to be 11.7%. The largest incidence is observed in sub-Saharan Africa (24%), Eastern Europe (21%) and Latin America (16%) (Bruni et al., 2010). Clinical studies have indicated that the highest prevalence of HPV infection is in women aged 15 to 19, with the highest incidence occurring in the 25th year (Muñoz et al., 2009). However, an increased incidence is observed in both developed and developing countries in women between the ages of 45 and 54 (Muñoz et al., 2004, Castle et al., 2005). The most common HPV genotype in women with normal cytology worldwide is HPV 16, followed by 18, 31, 58 and 52. HPV 16 is the most common genotype, with the exception of East Africa and Japan where HPV 52 prevails (de Sanjosé et al., 2007; Bruni et al., 2010).

The HPV in GREECE

In Greece, the incidence of HPV infection is high and is estimated to have been steadily rising in recent years. Most data on the incidence and prevalence of HPV infection in Greece are derived from the "LYSISTRATI" study (Table 1). Agorastos and his colleagues analyzing the final results of their study, aiming to assess the overall prevalence of HPV infection and the distribution of high risk types in Greek women aged 18 to 65, concluded that the prevalence was higher in the age group of 20 to 29 years, whereas an increased distribution was

observed in the age range of 50 to 59 years. Overall, 5.8% of women were positive in at least one high-risk HPV type. HPV 16 was the most commonly detected, followed by 31, 35, 53, 18, 51, 56, 58, 52, 39, 66, 45, 33, 59 and 68 genotypes. HPV 16 was detected in 24.8% of HPV positive women and in 1.4% of all women who participated in the study (Agorastos et al., 2009; Agorastos et al., 2014).

An older study, also from the Aristotle University of Thessaloniki, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection was 2.5% in a sample of approximately 1300 women, attending outpatient clinics in six gynecological departments in northern Greece. This low rate, one of the lowest recorded worldwide, was not considered reliable and it was attributed by the researchers to the fact that the individuals who participated in the study, were more aware of primary and secondary prevention issues of cervical cancer (Agorastos et al., 2004). An older epidemiological study in patients with both pathological cytological findings and cervical cancer, indicated that the high-risk HPV genotypes 16, 18 and 31 were detected in 56%, 23% and 6% respectively. HPV 16 was detected in 13% of low grade cervical lesions and 41% of high-grade cervical lesions. HPV 18 was detected in 13% and 14% of low grade and high grade intraepithelial cervical lesions respectively (Labropoulou et al., 1997).

In a similar epidemiological study, the purpose of which was to estimate the prevalence of HPV in the cervical cytology of a female population that followed up in outpatient clinics in Attica and to investigate the associated risk factors for acquiring HPV infection, it was concluded that the prevalence of HPV was higher among women of reproductive age. The HPV infection was detected in 22.7% of the above mentioned sample, with a peak prevalence of 56.9% in the age group from 21 to 30 years. The percentage of women diagnosed with HPV infection for the first time was 17.3%. Oncogenic HPV genotypes were detected in 14.2% of HPV positive women. The prevalence of high risk HPV subtypes 16, 53 and 18 was 5.3%, 4.9% and 0.9%, respectively. HPV 16 was the most common subtype isolated either alone, or in coexistence with other strains of the virus. Additionally, the authors have indicated that the number of sex partners and the amount of alcohol consumption, appear to be the most important risk factors for the development of HPV infection, followed by the young age and the low family income of the women studied (Stamataki et al., 2010).

Moreover, in a study conducted at the Oncologic Hospital in Athens from May 2003 to September 2006, with the participation of 1636 women aged 18 to 48 years, the prevalence of HPV infection was estimated to be 74.5% in women with pathological cytological findings and 24.6% in women with normal cytological findings. HPV was detected in 62.9% of cases of Atypical Squamous Cell of Undetermined Significance, 89.3% of low grade cervical intraepithelial lesions, 86.7% of high

Table 1. The prevalence of the HPV infection in Greece and the epidemiological classification of the virus subtypes by incidence

Study	Year	HPV Prevalence	HPV Genotypes
Agorastos et al	2014	5.8%	16, 31, 35, 53, 18, 51, 56, 58, 52, 39, 66, 45, 33, 59, 68
Kroupis et al	2007	23.6%	16, 58
Panotopoulou et al	2007	24.6%	11, 18, 6, 16, 31, 33
Stamataki et al	2010	22.7%	16, 53, 18

Table 2. The prevalence of the HPV infection in developed countries.

Country	HPV Prevalence	Country	HPV Prevalence
Sweden	20.3%	Austria	20.5%
Finland	7.8%	Germany	22.3%
Denmark	26.4%	France	45.3%
Italy	8.8%	Cyprus	72.8%
Spain	14.3%	USA	26.8%
Portugal	19.4%	Canada	46.9%
Great Britain	13.2%	China	38.9%

grade intraepithelial cervical lesions and 47.3% of cervical cancers. The most common subtype in the study sample was the HPV 11 - low risk subtype - with a detection rate of 13.4%. High-risk HPV 18 was detected at 10.3%. HPV 6, 16, 31 and 33 followed by 7.2%, 6.4%, 3.4% and 3.4% respectively (Panotopoulou et al., 2007).

Furthermore, another epidemiological study conducted in our country found that the prevalence of HPV infection in women with normal cervical cytology was 23.6%. The study included 841 women aged 16 to 72 years who were examined in a hospital in Attica, from 1998 to 2003. The HPV 16 was the most common type detected in the sample of the study. The HPV 58 subtype was associated with positive cytological findings of the women studied. In addition, as the age increases, a reduction in the prevalence of HPV is observed. The authors concluded that HPV infection, especially HPV 16, should be a major concern for Public Health in Greece (Kroupis et al., 2007).

In a study carried out in our country involving women from Crete and Central Greece, statistically significant differences between the two geographical regions with regard to the prevalence of HPV and the incidence of its subtypes were observed. Specifically, the prevalence of oncogenic HPV 18 subtype was higher in Crete than in Central Greece (29.7% vs. 13.1%). HPV 16 was detected more frequently in Central Greece (34.2%) than in Crete, where the prevalence was 23%. Other genotypes of HPV were more frequently detected among women from Central Greece than in women from Crete (52.6% vs. 45.9%). The authors concluded and confirmed the observation that the different frequencies of various HPV subtypes are not only between continents or countries, but also between different geographical regions of the same country (Mammas et al., 2008).

HPV in Europe and other Countries of the World

Prevalence of HPV infection in developed countries

Epidemiological studies from northern European countries (Table 2) indicated that the prevalence of HPV appears to be in line with data from studies carried out in Greece. With regard to the Scandinavian countries, a study conducted in Sweden and involving 539 women aged 19 to 25 with normal and pathological cytological findings, concluded that the prevalence of HPV infection was 20.3%, with a new infection rate of 17.3% (Evander et al., 1992). A recent study involving 6123 women aged 32 to 38, indicated that HPV infection by high risk subtypes was detected in 6.8% of the sample. HPV 16 was the most frequent type that was detected in 2.1%. HPV 31 (1.1%) was followed, whereas HPV types 18, 33, 35, 39, 45, 51, 52, 56, 58, 59 and 66 were detected in 3.6% of the women studied (Forslund et al., 2002). A recent survey from Finland indicated that in a total of 33043 women aged 25 to 65, 2574 women detected to be infected by HPV. The most common genotype was HPV 16, followed by 31 and 52 (Leinonen et al., 2013). Moreover, in a study conducted in Denmark in 2008, the prevalence of HPV infection was 26.4% (Kjaer et al., 2008). In a more recent survey involving 40000 women from Denmark, Nielsen and colleagues concluded that low-risk HPV types are present fairly frequently in ASCUS lesions, whereas low-risk HPV types without the coexistence of high-risk subtypes are never detected in severe cervical intraepithelial lesions (Nielsen et al., 2012).

A study from Central Europe and Austria, the sample of which included 542 women with an average age of 35.9 years, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection

was 20.5%. HPV 16 was the most common type and involved 6.5% of all infections. Less frequent were HPV 33 and HPV 31 genotypes, which were detected at 3.3% and 3%, respectively. Researchers noticed that younger age, smoking and multiple sex partners, constituted separate risk factors for the development of the HPV infection (Borena et al., 2016). An epidemiological study carried out in Germany involving approximately 1,700 women of childbearing age, showed that the prevalence of HPV infection (all types) was approximately 22.3%. In the 20 - 22 age group, the percentage was higher and was estimated at 28.3%. HPV genotypes 16, 42, 51 and 53 were the most frequently detected in the sample (Iftner et al., 2010). In contrast, in a study from Italy that included 1013 women aged 25 to 70 years with or without cytological findings, the prevalence of HPV infection was low (8.8%). The most common strain detected was HPV 16 (32.6%). High risk types were apparent in 7.1% of women and the incidence of multiple infections was 1.1%. HPV infection was more frequent in the age groups from 25 to 39 and 40 to 44 years, in a percentage of 13% - 14% and 11.5%, respectively. The inadequate recording of the data and the older age of the women who participated in the study, may also be the main reasons for the estimated low prevalence of HPV infection in this research (Ronco et al., 2005). Another survey from Italy indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection was high (37.7%), with high-risk genotypes detected in 30.9% of cases. The most common strain was HPV 16 (8.2%), followed by HPV 6 (5%), HPV 51 (4.2%) and HPV 53 (3.6%) (Capra et al., 2008).

A similar low prevalence of HPV infection was also estimated in Spain. According to the results of a multicenter study of 11 countries (Nigeria, India, Vietnam, Thailand, Korea, Colombia, Argentina, Chile, the Netherlands, Italy and Spain), the prevalence of the HPV infection was highest in Nigeria (25.6%) and less in Spain (1.4%) (Clifford et al., 2005). In the large CLEOPATRE study involving 3261 women from Spain aged 18 to 65 years, the prevalence of HPV infection was estimated at 14.3%. In the age group of young girls aged 18 to 25, the prevalence was twice as high (28.8%). High-risk genotypes were detected in 12.2% of the women studied. Multiple infections accounted for 4.1% of the total sample. The most common genotype detected was the oncogenic HPV 16 (2.9%), followed by 52, 51, 31 and 66 which were detected in 1.8%, 1.6%, 1.3% and 1.2% of the total population sample respectively (Castellsagué et al., 2012). The results of the study carried out in Portugal are similar. In a total of 2326 women, the prevalence of HPV infection was 19.4%, with HPV 16 being the most frequently detectable genotype in the study sample (Pista et al., 2011). An epidemiological study / meta - analysis involving approximately 5700 women from Great Britain and Ireland, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection, concerning the high - risk genotypes, was 13.2% (Anderson et al., 2013).

In contrast, an epidemiological survey carried out in France on a sample of 669 women of childbearing age, concluded that the prevalence of HPV infection was high and amounted to 45.3%. Among 34 different strains, HPV 16 was the most common type of virus and involved 32.6% of the women surveyed, followed by HPV 31 (7.4%), HPV 18 and 52 (6%), HPV 6 (5.3%) and HPV 66 (4.2%) (Pannier - Stockman et al., 2008). In addition, a study from Cyprus, the purpose of which was to estimate the prevalence of HPV infection and the distribution of HPV genotypes in women of childbearing age, concluded that the prevalence was quite high and amounted to 72.8%. The 59.4% of infected women were due to high-risk HPV types and the 34.8% of those, by low-risk ones. The most common type detected was HPV 16 (17.7%), followed by HPV 31, 58, 68, 18 and 56, that concerned the 12.9%, 7.1%, 4.6%, 4.1% and 3.7% of the individuals respectively (Krashias et al., 2017).

An epidemiological survey of women aged 14 to 59 years that carried out in the United States of America between 2003 and 2004, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection was 26.8%. At the same time, it was noticed that as the age increases the prevalence decreases: from 24.5% in the age group 14 to 19, to 19.6% in the 50-69 age group. The highest prevalence of HPV infection (44.8%) was detected in women aged 20-24 (Dunne et al., 2007). In 2011, Hariri and his colleagues found that the overall prevalence of any type of HPV, was 42.5% between 14 to 59 years. The greatest percentage (53.8%) in this study was once again observed in the 20-24 age group. The most common type detected was the low-risk HPV 62 (6.5%), followed by HPV 35 and HPV 16 in 4.7% of women (Hariri et al., 2011). Recently in 2017, the prevalence of HPV infection among women in the United States of America was estimated to be 26.8%, while in the male population was 45.2% (Han et al., 2017).

Furthermore, in a large epidemiological study / meta-analysis conducted in Canada, aiming to investigate the prevalence of HPV infection in women from 1960 to 2007, the highest prevalence was recorded among individuals younger than 20 years of age, decreasing in advanced ages. Thus, from 46.9% (14.1% - 46.9%) in girls aged less than 20 years, the prevalence of HPV infection decreased to 8.9% (2.5% - 8.9%) in the 50-69 age group. The most frequently noticed HPV genotype was 16, followed by HPV 18. HPV 16 was detected in 8.6% of the general population, 43.5% of all HPV positive women and 48.8% of women with confirmed cervical cancer. The researchers concluded that the oncogenic types of HPV 16 and 18, are responsible for about 2/3 of cervical cancers in Canada (Tricco et al., 2011). Epidemiological data from China recorded a prevalence of HPV infection of 38.9%, concerning all types of the virus in the study sample. The most common strain was HPV 52 (11%), followed by types 16, 58 and 53, which

Table 3. The prevalence of the HPV infection in developing countries.

Country	HPV Prevalence	Country	HPV Prevalence
Eastern Europe	12.6%	India	16.9%
Mexico	14.5%	Korea	38.8%
Argentina	16.6%	Vietnam	12.9%
Chile	14%	Sub-Saharan Africa	66.7%
Columbia	14.8%		

concerned 6.5%, 5.7% and 5.6% of the population of the study, respectively (Li et al., 2013).

Prevalence of HPV infection in developing countries

Epidemiological data from 16 developing countries in Central and Eastern Europe (Table 3), such as Albania, Bosnia and Herzegovina, Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Estonia, Hungary, Latvia, Lithuania, Poland, Romania, Serbia, Slovakia, Slovenia and the Former Yugoslav Republic of Macedonia, indicated that the average prevalence of HPV infection in women with normal uterine cervical cytology was 12.6%. HPV 16 was the most common detectable subtype. In the same survey the prevalence of HPV, among women with high intraepithelial cervical lesions and histologically diagnosed cervical cancer, was 78.1% and 86.6%, respectively, while HPV 16 and 18 were detected in 87.5% of the women studied (Poljak et al., 2013).

The prevalence of HPV infection in Mexico was investigated in a sample of 1340 women with normal cervical cytology and was 14.5% overall. In women under the age of 25, the prevalence was 16.7% and in those older than 65 years, reporting an active sex life, the HPV was detected at high enough levels (23%). HPV 16 was the most common type among affected individuals, followed by 53, 31, and 18 (Lazcano - Ponce et al., 2001). Similarly, HPV 16 was the most frequently detected type, in studies carried out in Argentina. Matos and colleagues in a survey involving 1028 women from Buenos Aires, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection was 16.6% (Matos et al., 2003). In a study from Santiago, Chile, the prevalence of HPV infection was 14%. HPV 16 was once again the most common type detected, followed by 56, 31, 58, 59, 18 and 52 (Ferreccio et al., 2004). In Colombia, a survey was conducted to assess the prevalence of HPV infection and the distribution of HPV genotypes in women with normal cervical cytology. It was concluded that the prevalence of the virus was 14.8%, remaining higher among women younger than 20 years (26.1%), while in females over 55 years it was significantly reduced. The HPV 16 genotype was the most commonly detected (16.3%), followed by 58, 56 and 18 (Molano et al., 2002).

In a study conducted in India involving approximately 1900 women aged 16 to 59, the prevalence of the HPV

was estimated to 16.9%. The infection was much more frequent in women with pathological cytological findings (73.9%), than in those with normal ones (14%). HPV 16 was the most common strain detected, followed by 56, 31, 33 and 18 (Franceschi et al., 2005). A study from Korea aiming to assess the prevalence of HPV among 1053 young students, 672 women and 381 men, indicated that the HPV infection, concerning the sexually active population, was apparent in 38.8% of women and 10.6% of males. The HPV 16 was the most detectable type (Shin et al., 2004). Furthermore, in a sample of about 2000 women aged 15 to 69 years old from Vietnam, the prevalence of HPV infection was about 12.9%. The most common type detected was HPV 16, followed by the HPV genotypes 58, 18 and 56 (Pham et al., 2003).

The prevalence of HPV infection was estimated to be 5 times higher in sub - Saharan Africa than in Europe, South America and Asia (Clifford et al., 2005). A recent epidemiological study in women of reproductive age, indicated that the prevalence of HPV infection in sub - Saharan Africa was 66.7%. The most commonly detectable HPV type was HPV 16 (11.7%), followed by 58, 51, 66, 18 and 81 at 10.3%, 8.9%, 8.6% and 7.6%, respectively (Mbulawa et al., 2018). In another study from South Africa, Ogembo and colleagues investigated the prevalence of HPV infection by the high-risk types 16 and 18, in women. They found out that the infection rate among individuals with normal cytological findings was 4.4% and 2.8%, respectively. In women with ASCUS the prevalence of the HPV 16 and 18 was 12% and 4.4%, whereas among individuals with low grade intraepithelial cervical lesions, was 14.5% and 10% respectively. In cases with high intraepithelial cervical lesions the detection rate of the above mentioned high-risk HPV genotypes, was 31.2% and 13.9% and in women with invasive cervical cancer of the uterus the prevalence of the HPV 16 and 18 was 49.7% and 18% respectively (Ogembo et al., 2015).

CONCLUSION

Regarding the global scale, the prevalence of the HPV infection in women with normal cytological findings is estimated to 11.7%. The highest incidence is observed in Sub - Saharan Africa (24%), Eastern Europe (21%) and

Latin America (16%). More often it affects women of childbearing age, with a greater incidence in their twenty-fifth year. Furthermore, the increased number of previous sex partners and the moderate to high alcohol consumption, appear to be the most important risk factors for the development of HPV infection, followed by the young age and the low socio - economic status of women. Globally, the most common HPV type detected in women with normal cytological findings is HPV 16, followed by the 18, 31, 58 and 52 subtypes. A geographical distribution of the above mentioned genotypes has been observed. Regarding Greece, several epidemiological studies have been carried out considering the prevalence of the virus. The similar results of the surveys have indicated that the age group with the most increased distribution is that of 20 to 29 years, which is in accordance to the international data. Although there was a decrease in the HPV prevalence as the age advances, a contradictory phenomenon was detected in some studies concerning the Greek population, in which the incidence of the HPV infection in postmenopausal patients aged 50 to 59 was elevated. The most common subtype detected was HPV 16, at rates ranging from 6.4% to 24.8%, followed by the HPV 18 in 0.9% to 29.7% and the HPV 11 in 13.4%. Following international standards, the incidence of the HPV subtypes has a specific geographical distribution. The prevalence of the HPV infection in women with normal cervical cytology was estimated to 23.6% - 24.6%, while the corresponding percentage for women with pathological cytological findings were 74.5%. In particular, the HPV virus was detected in 62.9% of ASCUS cases (Atypical Squamous Cell of Undetermined Significance) in 89.3% of low - grade cervical intraepithelial lesions, while it was responsible for the 86.7% of high-grade intraepithelial cervical lesions and the 47.3% of cases of cervical cancers. In Greece, the HPV 16 genotype was detected in 13% of the low grade and 41% of high - grade cervical lesions, while the HPV 18 was detected in 13% and 14% of low and high grade cervical intraepithelial lesions, respectively.

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